

Sample 07a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0448
{Fe}	40.4
{Si}	20.1
{Al, Si}	5.8
{Ca}	4.5
{Ca, Fe}	4.0
{Si, Fe}	2.6
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.3
{Mg, Si}	2.2
{Al, Si, Ca}	2.1
{Si, Ca HiP}	1.9
{Al, Ca}	1.8
{Mg, Fe}	1.5
{Al}	1.3
{S, Ca}	0.9
{Na, Al, Si}	0.8
{Al, Si, K}	0.7
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.6
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.6
{S, Ba-LA1}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{S}	0.3
{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
{Al, Fe}	0.3
{Mg}	0.3
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.3
{Mn}	0.3
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Si, K}	0.1
{P, Ca}	0.1
{S, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

141 μm

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	10.4
Pellet	3.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	18.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	5.4
BOF converter slag	2.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.5
Desulph slag	0.6
Ca-aluminate slag	1.6
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.6
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	6.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	5.5
Carbon rich - other	6.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.3
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	13.8
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	12.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	32.3
Site - ore / hot metal	5.4
Site - slag	5.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.9
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.6
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.3
Site - carbon-rich other	5.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	6.7
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.3
Urban	14.1
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	12.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 07b

Greyscale Image

100 µm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0406
{Fe}	43.6
{Si}	19.4
{Al, Si}	6.7
{Ca}	5.0
{Ca, Fe}	3.6
{Si, Fe}	2.6
{Mg, Si}	2.1
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.1
{Si, Ca HIP}	1.9
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.4
{Mg, Fe}	1.2
{Al, Ca}	1.1
{S, Ca}	1.0
{Al}	1.0
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.6
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
{Mg}	0.5
{S, Ba-LA1}	0.5
{Al, Si, K}	0.4
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
{S}	0.3
{Mg, Ca}	0.3
{Al, Fe}	0.3
{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.2
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Al}	0.1
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Si, K}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	9.6
Pellet	4.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	21.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	4.5
BOF converter slag	2.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.1
Desulph slag	0.7
Ca-aluminate slag	0.4
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.2
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	7.5
Carbon rich - other	7.0
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	9.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	12.4
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.2
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.1
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	35.5
Site - ore / hot metal	4.5
Site - slag	4.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.7
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.6
Site - carbon-rich other	7.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	7.0
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	9.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	12.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 07c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0382
{Fe}	48.4
{Si}	17.6
{Al, Si}	4.9
{Ca}	4.3
{Ca, Fe}	3.8
{Si, Fe}	2.8
{Mg, Si}	1.9
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.8
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.7
{Si, Ca HiP}	1.7
{Mg, Fe}	1.2
{Al}	0.9
{Al, Ca}	0.9
{S, Ca}	0.8
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.6
{Na, Al, Si}	0.6
{Al, Si, K}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.5
{S, Ba-LA1}	0.4
{Al, Fe}	0.4
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
{Mg}	0.3
{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
{S}	0.3
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.3
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{Mn}	0.1
{Si, K}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.1
{Mg, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	11.1
Pellet	5.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	23.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	7.4
BOF converter slag	2.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.2
Desulph slag	0.5
Ca-aluminate slag	0.5
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.3
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.1
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	3.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.9
Carbon rich - other	5.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.3
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	14.7
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	11.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.6
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.1
Unassigned other	0.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	39.5
Site - ore / hot metal	7.4
Site - slag	4.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.3
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.0
Site - carbon-rich other	2.9
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.3
Urban	15.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	11.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.6
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels